

Azolla growth in mud pots in summer, Tamil Nadu, India.

Pot capacity (litre)	Pot surface area (cm ²)	Mean azolla growth in water (g)	Mean azolla growth in soil extract (g)
2	176.8	21	23
3	314.3	23	25
5	452.6	25	26
8	616.0	14	19
10	804.5	13	14
CD		1.867	2.146

storage (see figure). The mud pots were made of fine alluvial soil and fired for 3 to 4 d. Similar pots are used to store and cool water in the local villages.

The soil extract was prepared by mixing 1 kg of clay soil with 1 litre of water and then filtering through muslin, Five ppm superphosphate was added to water and 10 ppm to soil with 20 ppm of carbofuran and carbendazim. Each pot

was inoculated with 20 g fresh azolla fronds, and kept in sunlight. Temperature was 35 to 39 °C. The biomass was recorded 10 d after inoculation. The 3- and 5-litre pots encouraged azolla growth (see table). Black rot developed in 8- and 10-litre pots because of the cooling effect. Pots with soil extract solutions were best for azolla maintenance at high temperatures. □

Yield response of rice to phosphorus

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We studied yield response of rice to P application at the Government Seed Farm, Rakh Mangan, in Dera Ismail Khan. Soil was a clay with 15% CaCO₃, pH 7.7, 0.8% organic matter, 5 ppm Olsen P, 150 ppm available K, and 0.04% N. Pretreatments were 0, 10, 20, or 30 ppm of fertilizer P to ensure that soils varied in initial available P content.

P treatments were in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications in 5- × 2-m plots. P was thoroughly mixed into the surface soil with basal doses of N and K. Plant height, panicles/m², and grain and straw yield were recorded and a combined analysis of the data was done by keeping soil types in main plots and P treatments in subplots.

Rice yielded significantly highest (7.4 t/ha) with 34 kg P/ha + NK (see table). Soil and treatment interactions also were significant. Straw yield and plant height were not significantly affected by P. Effect on number of panicles/m² was significant, and highest at 85 kg P/ha. The response to P treatment at initial soil P level was somewhat linear. As the initial soil P level increased, response to P treatment beyond 34 kg P/ha decreased (see figure). □

Response curves of P for rice at different initial soil P levels, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan.

Yield response of rice to P, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan.

Treatment (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha) at P content of				Mean yield (t/ha)	Mean straw yield (t/ha)	Mean panicles/m ²	Mean plant height (cm)
N	P	K	5 ppm	15 ppm	25 ppm	35 ppm				
0	0	0	4.4	4.1	4.8	3.3	5.1 d	7.7 b	248 c	100
100	0	75	5.5	5.1	5.5	5.5	5.4 c	12.4 a	325 ab	111
100	17	75	5.9	6.5	6.5	6.7	6.4 b	13.1 a	305 b	109
100	34	75	7.1	7.7	7.7	7.0	7.4 a	12.8 a	320 ab	111
100	51	75	7.1	6.1	6.8	6.7	6.7 b	12.9 a	320 ab	114
100	68	75	7.1	5.8	6.5	6.7	6.5 b	13.4 a	301 ab	115
100	85	75	7.7	5.5	6.4	6.7	6.6 b	13.7 a	331 a	112
Mean			6.40 a	5.82 b	6.31 ab	6.08 b				
Fertilizer					Significant			Significant	Significant	ns
Interactions (fertilizer × soils)					Significant			ns	Significant	ns
Soils					Significant			ns	ns	ns

Means followed by similar letters do not differ significantly from one another.

Management of aged seedlings of medium-duration rices

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We studied the response of 50-d-old IR20 seedlings in a factorial randomized block

Management of 50-d-old IR20 seedlings, Aduthurai, India, 1983-84 thaladi.

Basal N (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	10 × 10 cm	15 × 10 cm	20 × 10 cm
50	3.0	2.8	2.9
62.5	3.1	3.0	3.1
75	3.3	3.4	3.7
Mean	3.1	3.1	3.2

CD (P = 0.05)

Spacing : NS
Nitrogen : 0.34
S × N : 0.58

design with 4 replications of 3 spacings (10- × 10-cm, 15- × 10-cm, and 20- × 10-m) and 3 basal N rates: recommended dose, 50 kg N/ha; 25% more N, 62.5 kg N/ha; and 50% more N, 75 kg N/ha. All treatments were topdressed with urea at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits at 15-d intervals.

Soil was clay loam with pH 7.5, low available N, and medium P and K.

Planting aged seedlings at close spacing did not significantly increase yield. Basal application of 75 kg N/ha gave significantly higher yield. Interactions between spacing and N application rates were

significant. At 10- × 10-cm spacing, there was no significant yield difference between N application rates, but at 15- × 10-cm and 20- × 10-cm, yield increased significantly with more N. The 20- × 10-cm spacing and basal 75 kg N/ha gave the highest yield (see table). □

Stubble management for summer lowland rice

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We evaluated stubble management to reduce the required fertilizer application for lowland rice in Jan-Feb 1982-84 at TNAU. Co 43 was planted the first season and IR20 the second. The soil was a clay loam with pH 8.0-8.5 (1:2.5 soil water ratio). Temperature varied from 17°C to 30°C during the cropping season.

N content of the stubble was 0.4-0.5% by weight. Stubbles of different heights were left in the field after harvest and plow-incorporated, then 22 kg P as powdered rock phosphate and 42 kg K as muriate of potash were applied. One week to 10 d after stubble incorporation,

Effect of stubble incorporation on N application and grain yield, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Summer 1982-83	Summer 1983-84
Recommended dose (100-22-42 kg NPK/ha)	5.2	6.5
15-cm stubble + 25% N	4.3	5.1
30-cm stubble + 25% N	3.2	5.2
45-cm stubble + 25% N	4.0	5.0
15-cm stubble + 50% N	3.8	5.0
30-cm stubble + 50% N	5.0	5.2
45-cm stubble + 50% N	5.4	6.6
15-cm stubble + 75% N	4.4	5.6
30-cm stubble + 75% N	4.4	5.3
15 cm stubble + 15% N	4.1	5.8
CD	0.6	0.7

the field was plowed again, leveled, and the second rice crop planted. Results showed that with stubble incorporation chemical N application could be reduced without yield loss (see table).

In both years, 45-cm-tall stubble with 50% of the normal N fertilizer yielded highest among treatments and at par with the recommended application of 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha. □

Response of lowland rice to fertilizer application

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Often, a rice crop does not yield well even after liberal application of NPK. Next to N,

P deficiency can be a major constraint to yield. Experiments to identify reasons for low yield indicate Zn deficiency limits rice production in Punjab. S deficiency can also be a constraint.

We studied the response of rice to balanced nutrient application based on general recommendations and soil analysis

Soil characteristics of fields at experiment sites in Punjab, India.

Site	Texture	pH	E. C. (mmho/cm)	Organic carbon (%)	Available p ^a (kg/ha)	Available K ^b (kg/ha)
1	Sandy loam	8.7	0.20	0.48	7.5	465
2	Sandy loam	9.0	0.30	0.38	10.0	450
3	Sandy loam	9.0	0.30	0.33	10.0	420
4	Sandy loam	9.2	0.30	0.21	10.0	412
5	Sandy loam	8.8	0.30	0.45	12.5	262

^aDetermined in Olsen's extract (0.5 N NaHCO₃ solution: pH 8.5). ^bExtracted with neutral normal ammonium acetate solution.

Grain yield (t/ha)

Response of rice to fertilizers (mean of 5 sites).